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ABSTRACT

Here we present measurements of dissociative and non-dissociative cross-sections for the electron impact of the CF₄ molecule. The present experiments are based on a Recoil Ion Momentum Spectrometer (*RIMS*), a standard gas mixing setup for CF₄, and a reference gas. The measurements were carried out at several electron energies up to 1 keV, covering the energy range of previous experiments. We apply the relative flow technique (*RFT*) to convert the relative cross-sections measured by the *RIMS* into absolute values. Using the combination of *RIMS* and *RFT*, ion collection and calibration errors were minimized. The results were compared with theoretical and experimental studies available in the literature. Previous electron impact experiments present relative cross-sections or use correction terms for the absolute cross-sections due to losses of energetic ions. We elucidate the differences between the new measurement method and the existing ones in the literature and explain why the present method can be considered reliable. Furthermore, we show how reducing correction terms affects the results.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Fully or partly halogenated hydrocarbons such as perfluorocarbons (*PFCs*), chlorofluorocarbons (*CFCs*), and hydrochlorofluorocarbons (*HCFCs*) are among the most potent atmosphere-damaging molecules listed under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (*UNFCCC*).^{1,2} Perfluorocarbons (*PFCs*) are potent greenhouse gases (*GHGs*) with exceedingly long atmospheric lifetimes of 10 000 to more than 50 000 years. CF₄ (*PFC* – 14) is the simplest *PFC* with the longest-lived greenhouse gas known currently estimated at 50 000 years representing a permanent alteration to the atmosphere.³ They accumulate in the lower layer of the atmosphere, the troposphere, absorb infrared radiation, and trap heat in the atmo-

sphere, which results in continuous global warming and climate change.

Several experimental studies on the ionization by electron impact of *PFCs* (like CF₄) are reported in the literature, where different methodologies are employed. Christophorou and co-workers (Refs. 4–6) compiled the available information on total and partial electron impact cross-sections (*TICS* and *PICS*, respectively). In their first work in 1996,⁴ they presented a compilation of electron impact cross-section measurements, and based on the assessment of that data, they recommended values for various *TICS* and *PICS*. Later in 1999,⁵ they updated their previously recommended cross-sections by including data from the *TICS* of Rao and Srivastava⁷ and Nishimura *et al.*⁸ In 2004,⁶ they added data on the *TICS* and *PICS* of Sieglaff *et al.*^{9–11} and *TICS* of Bart *et al.*¹²

In this work, we describe a new methodology to determine absolute *TICS* and *PICS* by applying three-dimensional ion imaging using a recoil ion momentum spectrometer (*RIMS*)¹³ and a mixing target gas setup. The mixing setup procedures apply the known relative flow technique (*RFT*)¹⁴ and were implemented to convert the relative cross-sections measured by the *RIMS* into absolute values. The validation of the method was applied to CF_4 as a test molecule, which, after ionization, ejects energetic ions. The *RIMS* makes it possible to analyze the energy distribution of the ions and to judge if ions are not fully collected. In addition, choosing the conditions and the reference gas appropriately in the mixing target procedure avoids inaccuracies in the conversion of relative cross sections into absolute ones.^{15,16} The goal after validation of the methodology is to apply it to other molecules, such as halogenated hydrocarbons, chloro- and fluorocarbons, and hydrochloro- and hydrofluorocarbons. For comparison with our results, we will use the cross-sections of Refs. 5 and 6 throughout this work.

It is important to note that large discrepancies are found in published total and partial ionization cross-section data⁶ (see Figs. 1 and 4). The origin of these differences in the cross-sections could be mainly due to two factors: the normalization procedure and the collection efficiency of the ionic energetic species resulting from molecular dissociation. One of the goals of the methodology presented here was to avoid the use of adjusting terms obtained by simulations and corrections related to discrimination effects. The loss of specific fragment ions in the spectrometer due to their excess kinetic energies leads to reduced ion collection efficiency. Another constraint in the measurements is the micro-channel plate (*MCP*) efficiency, which depends on the molecular mass of the ion, its impacting kinetic energy on the *MCP*, and the open area ratio (*OAR*) of the *MCP*, which must be taken into account.

In Sec. II, we present in detail the experimental set-up and data analysis procedure, based on the electron projectile-recoil ion detection technique that enables the measurement of absolute total and partial molecule ionization cross-sections for an effusive gas mixture jet target set-up. The method is applied to the ionization of CF_4 by electron impact with energies ranging from 30 to 1000 eV.

The results of the measurements are presented and compared with available experimental and theoretical data in Sec. III. It is divided into subsections, where the discussions are focused on comparing the experimental methods previously used and the derived data. In Sec. IV, the results are summarized.

II. METHODS

The recoil ion momentum spectrometer (*RIMS*) and the relative flow technique (*RFT*) setups used in the present study are described in the following.

A. Recoil ion momentum spectrometer technique (*RIMS*)

The recoil ion momentum spectrometer (*RIMS*) configuration used to measure *TICS*s and *PICS*s has been described elsewhere¹⁷ and a description is presented here, including modifications performed on the setup. A schematic drawing of the setup is shown in Fig. 1.

The pulsed-electron-beam time-of-flight mass spectrometer apparatus was modified by the addition of a needle required for studies where the use of a supersonic gas jet is not feasible. One of the main reasons why supersonic jets cannot be used is due to the limited availability of gas samples, as in the case of perfluorocarbons (*PFC*s), chlorofluorocarbons (*CFC*s), and hydrochlorofluorocarbons (*HCFC*s) molecules, which will be consumed very quickly if used with the supersonic jets. The ions produced from the electron-molecule collisions were measured using *RIMS* with a crossed geometry of electron and molecular beams. The electron beam is pulsed at a repetition rate of 15.75 kHz by applying a voltage pulse with a length of 200 ns. It is focused close to the exit of a needle by three lenses and magnetically guided by Helmholtz coils placed outside the vacuum chamber. This needle with an inner diameter of 1.0 mm is pointing out parallel to the pusher plate and perpendicular to the time-of-flight spectrometer axis, therefore expanding the gas into the interaction region. The effusive gas flow is controlled by a precision leak valve and the pressure in the chamber

FIG. 1. Illustration of the electron gun, the ion momentum spectrometer (sections allow views of electron and ion trajectories), and the gas mixing setup. The supersonic gas jet above the spectrometer was not in operation in this work.

is kept around 1.5×10^{-7} mbar during operation of the gas beam. The target density in the effusive beam is at least two orders of magnitude higher than in the supersonic gas jet and the gas is at room temperature.

The ionized species created in a collision are collected by a short two-stage spectrometer with a total length of 11 cm and nine electrode rings of 9 cm inner diameter, each set at 10 mm apart, divided into three sections. The drift length is twice the acceleration length satisfying the Wiley–McLaren geometry¹⁸ for the time-focusing condition. This is needed to prevent the spread of flight times of the ions with different starting positions due to the size of the interaction region of 2 mm along the spectrometer axis. The first two electrodes (electrodes 1 and 2), as shown in Fig. 1, define the pusher region, where the needle is positioned at half the distance between them. While the projectile pulse traverses the spectrometer, the interaction region is kept field-free to avoid any deflection of the electron beam. With a delay of 100 ns, voltage pulses of +100 V and +40 V are applied to the pusher electrode 1 and the needle, respectively. Thus, the ions are extracted from the interaction region and pushed into the acceleration section. This region is defined by the set of electrodes from 2 to 5, which are connected in series by 100 k Ω resistors, where electrode 2 is at ground and electrode 5 at -184 V. The voltage gradient of 224 V/35 mm accelerates and drives the ions into a

field free region of 70 mm defined by electrodes 5–9 and two subsequent grids kept at -184 V. A homogeneous and strong electric field is applied between the final grid and front of the MCPs set at -184 and -2600 V, respectively, accelerating the ions to higher energies before hitting the front MCP.

The pulse settings on the spectrometer, pusher, and needle are triggered by the same signal applied to the electron beam, and pusher plate and needle voltages are set by distinct pulse generators with filters defining quite sharp rise and fall signals. Different voltage settings on the pusher and needle were probed with commitment to optimize the time-focusing condition as well as the detection of the momenta distributions of the ions.

Time difference between the electron pulse signal and the MCP signal provides the time of flight information. The electron cloud produced by the MCPs hits on a position-sensitive delay-line anode (DLDA configuration), which records the X and Y-hit position distribution of the ions on the detector.¹⁹ The time and hit position signals are fed to a multi-hit time-to-digital converter, and the raw data events are recorded in list file mode by the *Cobold* data acquisition and analysis software.²⁰ The X–Y coordinates of the setup are defined as follows: the X-axis (horizontal) is along the electron beam and the Y-axis (vertical) is perpendicular to the electron beam and the extraction direction (Fig. 1).

FIG. 2. (a) 2D-map of the Y position on the detector and time-of-flight of a 200 eV electron- CF_4 collision. (b) Projection onto the Y-axis of the 2D-map. The intensities are in log scale. (c) Projection onto the horizontal axis (X-axis) of the 2D-map corresponds to the time-of-flight of the first ion (T_1) that reaches the detector, T_1 spectrum. The yields are shown on a linear scale. The *krypton* ions are highlighted in gray filled pattern.

The majority of the dissociating ions of CF_4 can have high kinetic energies that can reach up to 15 eV in dissociative double ionization channels.^{21–23} To collect those ions that are emitted in the transversal plane, a detector with large MCPs of 80 mm in diameter in a chevron configuration is used. Figure 2(a) shows a two dimensional map (2D-map) of the Y position and time-of-flight distribution of the ions for events coming from single hits with 200 eV collision energy.

The projection onto the Y-axis of the 2D map shown in Fig. 2(b) reveals that essentially all ions with low to high momenta/kinetic energies are collected. There are no significant losses due to the kinetic energy of the ions. The sharp drop in intensity shown at $Y = 39$ mm in Fig. 2(b) indicates that a small fraction of the F^+ distribution is not measured. It was determined to be below 1% and can be considered negligible [see the intensity log scale in Fig. 2(b)]. The projection onto the X-axis of the 2D-map corresponds to the time of flight spectrum of single ions of CF_3 and Kr (T_1 spectrum). The TOF peaks of CF_3^+ , CF_2^+ , CF^+ , F^+ , CF_3^{2+} , and CF_2^{2+} as well as of the mixing gas krypton, Kr^+ , Kr^{2+} , and Kr^{3+} , clearly discriminated in gray filled pattern, can be observed in Fig. 2(c). The time resolution of the setup allowed the discrimination of krypton isotopes, which occur in nature as a mixture of six different, stable isotopes with masses of 78 (0.4%), 80 (2.3%), 82 (11.6%), 83 (11.5%), 84 (57.0%), and 86 (17.3%). The parent ion CF_4^+ is not expected to be detected because its ionic states are not stable but dissociate within femtoseconds.¹¹ The production of CF_3^+ dominates over other dissociation channels, which are almost an order of magnitude smaller.

The axial symmetric construction of the recoil ion spectrometer (Fig. 1) images the longitudinal (p_z) and transversal momentum components of ions ($\sqrt{p_x^2 + p_y^2}$). The longitudinal Z component p_z relies on the time-of-flight of the ion, and the transversal X and Y components depend on the hit (X, Y) position of the ion on the detector and its TOF. The momenta are derived by applying Newton's equations of motion. Figure 3 shows the image for the hit X–Y position of the CF_3^+ ion on the detector for impact of 200 eV

FIG. 3. X–Y position image of CF_3^+ for incident 200 eV electrons.

electrons, selecting the events correlated with the time-of-flight of the CF_3^+ ion.

The ion–ion pair production was also measured as shown in Fig. 4(a). The figure presents the 2D-map of coincident ion–ion detection, where the horizontal and vertical axes denote the TOF of the first and second ions to reach the detector, respectively. The fragmentation channel $\text{CF}_4^{2+} \rightarrow \text{CF}_3^+ + \text{F}^+$ is a pure Coulomb-explosion channel, while all others are incomplete Coulomb-explosion channels, where three or more species are generated involving the ejection of neutral fragments: $\text{CF}_2^+ + \text{F}^+ + \text{F}$, $\text{CF}^+ + \text{F}^+ + 2\text{F}$, $\text{C}^+ + \text{F}^+ + 3\text{F}$ and $\text{F}^+ + \text{F}^+ + \text{CF}_2$. As outlined, in the five dominating channels, the major ion–ion pair formation corresponds to the ejection of one fluorine atomic ion. To the extent that this assumption is valid, Fig. 4(b) depicts the projection onto the vertical axis (Y-axis) of the 2D-map for two T_1 time windows, as indicated by the red and blue boxes in Fig. 4(a). This produces two coincidence

FIG. 4. (a) 2D-map of coincident ion–ion detection, where the horizontal and vertical axes denote the TOF of the first and second ions to reach the detector, respectively. The electron energy is 200 eV. (b) The red and blue curves correspond to the projection of the events within red and blue boxes, respectively, onto the vertical axis of the 2D-map for T_1 intervals as indicated in (a). This produces two coincidence spectra where the first ion detected was C^+ (red) and F^+ (blue), respectively. (c) TOF spectrum of single events showing for comparison the intensities of the dissociative single ionization channels.

spectra (T_2 -coinc spectra) where the first ion detected was C^+ (red) and F^+ , respectively. Figure 4(c) presents the TOF spectrum of single events showing the intensities of the dissociative single ionization channels [Fig. 2(c)]. Here, Fig. 4(c) is included for a better comparison of the contribution of the low intensity fragmentation channels for single ionization with the intensities of the same fragments originating from double ionization. For all measured electron impact energies, the event counts from dissociative double ionization are lower than those from dissociative single ionization as shown in Figs. 4(b) and 4(c). Triple ionization was considered negligible as already verified in Ref. 23. The detector counting rate was maintained at around 1000 counts/s compared to a projectile pulse rate of 15.75 kHz to avoid a high random coincidence rate.

The single ionization intensities of the CF_3 and Kr ions are extracted from the T_1 spectrum [Fig. 2(c)], while the double ionization ones from the T_2 -coincidence spectrum [Fig. 4(b)]. Some corrections, for example, for finite detector efficiencies, are needed to obtain the true counts that originate from these channels. The following convention is used for the single ionization: $N^{true}(Y^+)$ denotes the true number of events when CF_4 dissociates into a neutral X and a Y^+ ion, and $N^{mea}(Y^+)$ denotes the numbers of measured events (peak area). Similar conventions are applied for double ionization when an ion-ion pair X^+ and a Y^+ are created. Equations (1)–(4) below provide the true counts $N^{true}(Y^+)$ for the CF_4 and Kr ion species from the measured ones, $N^m(Y^+)$ and $N^m(X^+, Y^+)$, where Y stands for Kr, C, F, CF, CF_2 , and CF_3 , and X for F and C, and ε is the efficiency of the detection system for each ionic species. For the parent ions only, the correction for detection efficiency applies:

$$N^{true}(CF_4^+, Kr^+) = \frac{N^{mea}(CF_4^+, Kr^+)}{\varepsilon_Y}. \quad (1)$$

On the other hand, for single dissociative ionization, two terms are needed:

$$N^{true}(Y^+) = \frac{N^m(Y^+)}{\varepsilon_Y} - \frac{(1 - \varepsilon_X)}{\varepsilon_X \varepsilon_Y} \times N^{mea}(X^+, Y^+). \quad (2)$$

The first term corrects the single ionization counts concerning the ion detection efficiency, while the second one takes into account false counts from double ionization. If only one ion of an ion pair is detected, this contributes as a false event to the singles spectrum. It will be measured as a single charge event producing an artificial enhancement of the single ionization channels. Therefore, it is necessary not only to correct for the detection efficiencies but also to subtract the false events.^{24–27} The strongest contribution of false events stems from fluorine atomic ions, as evaluated from the T_2 -coincidence spectrum in Fig. 4(b).

The next equation corrects the double ionization events for ion-ion pair detection efficiencies. The true counts in this case are enhanced much more than the single ionization events due to double detection efficiency factors:

$$N^{true}(X^+, Y^+) = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_X \varepsilon_Y} \times N^{mea}(X^+, Y^+). \quad (3)$$

The last expression deals with doubly charged ions, where a similar correction applied for the parent ion [Eq. (1)] is used:

$$N^{true}(CF_{2,3}^{2+}) = \frac{N^{mea}(CF_{2,3}^{2+})}{\varepsilon_Y}. \quad (4)$$

For comparison, electron impact measurements on CF_4 were done using a high resolution time-of-flight mass reflectron spectrometer. A detailed description of the setup is reported in Ref. 28. For 200 eV electrons, Fig. 5 shows the time-of-flight spectrum acquired by the reflectron, which is indicated by a red solid line superimposed with the present measurements described by a blue solid line. It demonstrates clearly the disadvantage of measuring absolute cross-sections with such a spectrometer. The comparison between the T_1 spectrum measured with the RIMS setup and the reflectron one shows that the latter was adequate for high mass resolution measurement of all ions produced in the electron-molecule collision, but on the other hand, the ions emitted with high momenta/kinetic energies were not fully collected [Figs. 5(a)–5(c)]. The line structure with two maxima for an individual ionic fragment stems from losses of ions, which are emitted transversally to the spectrometer axis. These ions have small longitudinal momenta and would show up in the line center. On the other hand, the spectrometer has higher acceptance for ions emitted forward and backward along the spectrometer axis with small transversal momentum, which result in the two observed peaks. Only simulations with previous knowledge of the kinetic energy distribution of each fragment ion species can correct these data. The peak intensities of all spectra shown were normalized to the peak maxima of the CF_3^+ .

FIG. 5. (a) Comparison of the time-of-flight spectra measured at electron energy 200 eV with the RIMS setup and the reflectron spectrometer showing the full range of masses indicated by the blue and red lines, respectively. (b) Only CF_3^+ and (c) only CF^+ .

B. Relative flow technique (RFT)

The recorded intensities of the ions measured by the *RIMS* were converted into absolute ionization cross-sections using the *RFT*.^{14,29–31} Here, the CF_4 gas is mixed with an equal amount of the reference gas krypton, for which accurate absolute cross section data are available. To prepare the mixed gas sample, CF_4 gas and the Kr reference gas were filled first into a small reservoir in equal amounts (50 mbar each), which were measured with a capacitance manometer (Fig. 1). Then the mixed gas was allowed into a second reservoir with a four times larger volume than the small one. Diffusion leads to the mixing of the two gases until the distribution is uniform throughout the volume. Since the diffusion time required to achieve equilibrium distribution is proportional to gas pressure and, therefore, inversely proportional to the volume,³² the larger reservoir is advantageous for faster mixing. Then, a second gate valve is opened, and the mixture is injected into the system through an ultra-fine leak valve and a capillary needle. The flow was monitored by measuring the increase in chamber pressure before starting the measurements and after stopping the experiments, and the pressure in the injection line was monitored constantly. It was verified that the volume of gas loaded in the large reservoir and the flow controlled by the leak valve were set in the best condition and that changes in pressure were negligible.

Krypton ($M = 84$ a.u.) was chosen for its proximity in mass to the CF_4 ($M = 88$ a.u.) molecule to guarantee homogeneity in the gas mixing ratio during the molecular flow through the ultra-fine leak valve and needle and for similar detection efficiency.³³ The cross-sections are defined as follows:

$$\frac{N_{\text{CF}_4}^{\text{true}}}{N_{\text{Kr}}^{\text{true}}} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{CF}_4}}{\sigma_{\text{Kr}}} \frac{\beta_{\text{CF}_4}}{\beta_{\text{Kr}}} \sqrt{\frac{M_{\text{CF}_4}}{M_{\text{Kr}}}}, \quad (5)$$

where σ refers to the ionization cross-section, β is related to the interaction volume defined by the intersection between the gas and the electron beam,²⁹ and M is the molecular weight. The mass factor represents the ratio of flow rates of the gases through the needle (Fig. 6).

Knowledge of the molecular beam profile is especially important when used in quantitative measurements of cross-sections.^{14,34–36} The beam profile of the gas beam depends primarily

FIG. 6. Schematic diagram of crossed beams, where i is the beam current, β is the interaction volume, and n is the density of the gases.

on the gas mean free path. According to accepted procedures, the driving pressure P_s behind the needle should be such that the mean free paths are equal according to their gas-kinetics diameters. CF_4 and Kr possess similar atomic weights and similar gas kinetics, resulting in similar mass flow rates. Therefore, the beam profiles of the two gases can be considered closely the same:

$$\frac{\beta_{\text{CF}_4}}{\beta_{\text{Kr}}} = \frac{R_{\text{CF}_4}}{R_{\text{Kr}}}. \quad (6)$$

The relative flow rate R is related to the outflow of gases P_s from the reservoir at the steady-state condition. In the intermediate flow regime, R is given by

$$R = aP_s(1 + \alpha P_s), \quad (7)$$

where the first and second terms are the rates due to the free-molecular and the binary-collision processes, respectively.³⁴ For the range of driving pressures P_s where inter-atomic-molecular collisions within the tube are negligible, the constant factor a is inversely dependent on \sqrt{M} , the molar mass number. The product $a\alpha$ is proportional to δ^2/\sqrt{M} , where δ is the kinetic molecular diameter³⁷ (for CF_4 and Kr $\delta = 0.47$ and 0.38 nm, respectively³⁸). Equation (6) implies a ratio, and the pressure-dependent expression $1 + \alpha P_s$ in the numerator and denominator would not change much the results due to a possibly nonlinear relation between the flow rate and pressure. The working pressures and lengths of the tubes and needle determine that the present measurements are operated mainly in free molecular flow.

The true intensities of the CF_4 ions $N_{\text{CF}_4}^{\text{true}}(E_i, Y)$ are converted into absolute ionization cross-sections at electron energies E_i of the ion species Y as defined in Eq. (2), applying the following expression:

$$\sigma_{\text{CF}_4}(E_i, Y) = \sigma_{\text{Kr}}(E_i, \text{Kr}^+) \frac{N_{\text{CF}_4}^{\text{true}}(E_i, Y)}{N_{\text{Kr}}^{\text{true}}(E_i, \text{Kr}^+)}, \quad (8)$$

where the single ionization electron impact cross-sections of Kr are taken from Rejoub *et al.* and Krishnakumar *et al.* $\sigma_{\text{Kr}}(E_i, \text{Kr}^+)$,^{39,40} and the present measured true intensity of the single ionized Kr^+ , $[N_{\text{Kr}}^{\text{true}}(E_i, \text{Kr}^+)]$ events, with efficiency ϵ_{Kr^+} were considered for normalization [see Eq. (1)].

C. Mixing gas procedures

1. Detector efficiency procedures

The ion detection efficiencies of the MCP depend on different factors such as its open area, the MCP operating voltage, the ion mass/charge ratio, and the impact energy of the ions on the MCP. The MCPs used in the experiment were standard ones with an open area of 52%. The operating voltage was maximized, and the threshold adjustment of the constant fraction discriminator for the MCP signal was minimized. The ions were pre-accelerated by -2600 V before hitting the MCP. For the analysis of the relative cross sections for different ions, it must be considered that ions with a high mass/charge ratio are usually detected with less efficiency than those with lower ones. There are several procedures described in the literature for determining the detection efficiencies of MCPs.^{33,41–49} In the present work, the detector efficiency approach recommended by Krems *et al.* was followed.³³ They provide an analytic formula

FIG. 7. Ratios of the detection efficiency of Kr^+ and efficiencies of CF_4 fragment ions $\varepsilon_{\text{Kr}}(\text{Kr}^+)/\varepsilon_{\text{CF}_4}(a)$ as used in the present data analysis.

to express the efficiencies for ions that scale to a single curve as a function of the impact energy divided by the square root of the ion mass.^{33,41} To reduce the influence of this correction on the absolute cross section calibration procedure, it is desirable to have similar efficiencies for the ions from the reference gas and the ions from CF_4 .

The ratios of the efficiency for Kr^+ and efficiencies for CF_4 fragment ions ($\varepsilon_{\text{Kr}}(\text{Kr}^+)/\varepsilon_{\text{CF}_4}(a)$) adopted in the analysis are shown in Fig. 7. They range from 0.95 for CF_3^+ down to 0.69 for the lighter C^+ .

2. Reference gas krypton

To test our absolute cross section calibration method and in particular the detector efficiencies entering, we produced absolute cross-sections of Kr^{2+} and compared with literature data. Therefore, as described in Eqs. (1) and (8), the true intensities of the krypton ions Kr^+ and Kr^{2+} were obtained from the measured line intensities and the detection efficiencies. Finally, using these true intensities and published absolute cross-sections for Kr^+ , the $\sigma_{\text{Kr}}(E_i, \text{Kr}^{2+})$ was calculated. A comparison of $\sigma_{\text{Kr}}(E_i, \text{Kr}^{2+})$ between the present derived values and literature values of $\sigma_{\text{Kr}}(E_i, \text{Kr}^{2+})$ (Fig. 8) shows good agreement, providing confidence that the present measurements and the evaluation of the ion detection efficiencies are reliable.^{39,40,50–54}

3. Density of mixing gases

The linearity in the ion production with the density of the samples in the gas mixture was examined for different pressure ratios (R_{gas}) of the CF_4 and Kr. Primarily, equal pressures of 50 mbar for both gases were selected. Then the production of CF_3^+ and Kr^+ for the mixing ratios 3:1, 2:1, 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 of CF_4 and Kr gases were measured. In a second step, the ratio of $N^+(\text{CF}_3^+)$ to $N^+(\text{Kr}^+)$ (R_{counts}) was divided by the respective gas mixing ratios (R_{gas}), and an average constant value was obtained (Fig. 9). This result shows that both gases are mixed homogeneously and the flow rates are in accordance with their mixing ratios.

III. RESULTS

From the theoretical side, several calculations of total ionization cross-sections as a function of electron energy are available

FIG. 8. Absolute ionization cross-section of Kr^{2+} $\sigma_{\text{Kr}^{2+}}$ as a function of the electron energy of present work indicated in black solid squares compared with literature values shown in open symbols.

FIG. 9. Comparison of gas mixing ratios. Ratios of $N^+(\text{CF}_3^+)$ to $N^+(\text{Kr}^+)$ in black solid line and square symbols and normalized ratios $R_{\text{counts}}/R_{\text{gas}}$ in red solid line and squares (see text).

in the literature based on different models in an effort to improve the agreement between models and accessible experimental data at the time of the calculations. The most widely accepted models are the binary-encounter-Bethe *BEB* and dipole *BED* method,^{55–57} the Deutsch and Märk *DM* formalism,⁵⁸ and the modified additivity rule *MAR*.⁵⁹ In the case of molecules containing heavy atoms, like fluorine, electron correlations and empirical corrections have been introduced to improve the calculations. For example, Deutsch and Märk modified the Lotz formulas for molecules containing fluorine to describe the cross-section anomaly of fluorine molecules.⁶⁰ In Fig. 10, the present data are compared to several calculations and to Christophorou *et al.*^{4–6} recommended values, and an average of the results of some datasets.

Binary-Encounter-dipole Bethe (*BEB*) and Binary-Encounter-dipole Born (*BED*) models known as classical-*BEB*,^{61,62} *Kim-BEB*,^{12,55,63} *RHF-BEB* (restricted Hartree Fock wave functions-*BEB*),⁸ *CAS-BEB* (complete-active-space SCF wave functions-*BEB*),⁸ *AE-BEB* (all electrons *BEB*),⁶⁴ *siBEB*,⁸ *ECP-BEB* (effective core potentials-*BEB*),⁶⁴ α -*BEB* (target polarizability *BEB*),⁶⁴ Additivity rule-*BEB*,⁶² *siBED* (simplified *iBED*⁶⁵ with shielding long-range dipole potential),⁶³ semiempirical Harland

FIG. 10. Absolute single ionization cross-section of CF_4 σ_{TOTAL} of the present work compared to theoretical calculations available in the literature as a function of the electron energy. The error bar is indicated on the 100 eV electron energy data.

and Vallance (*HV*)^{10,66} *DM* methods,^{10,12} and Modified Additivity Rule (*MAR*) formalism¹⁰ were proposed to best describe the CF_4 experimental cross-sections in shape, energy of the maxima, and the maximum of the total ionization cross-section. Molecular *ab initio* information required by the *BEB*, *BED*, and *DM* models were included in the calculations at several quantum chemistry levels and a series of basis sets, with and without electron correlation, *Jahn–Teller* splitting, and interaction potentials.

The peak maxima of the theoretical cross-sections range from $4 \times 10^{-20} \text{ m}^2$ ⁶⁴ in better agreement with the present value to $10 \times 10^{-20} \text{ m}^2$.⁶² The positions of the maxima vary from 75⁶² to 140 eV.^{12,63} The present data do not allow the precise determination of the energy position of the maximum, and for that purpose, additional measurements are needed around electron energies of 100 eV.

The CF_4 molecule is one of the most experimentally studied fluoromethanes. Figure 11 shows the present data and collects the sets of reported single ionization cross-section Refs. 8–10, 12, and 67–73. The doubly ionized meta-stable ions CF_2^{2+} and CF_3^{2+} were not included in the single ionization cross-section evaluation.

The uncertainties of the present data are the combined uncertainties present in the two techniques, yielding in total and statistical uncertainties of around 10%. The accuracy limit of extracting the ion's intensities was estimated to be significantly smaller, as all ions were well distinguished from each other by their time-of-flight and full momentum. The density proportion of the gas mixture (1:1) was well fixed by selecting a total gas pressure (100 mbar) in the small container. The uncertainties in previous absolute cross-section measurements are partially due to the various corrections applied.

In all the datasets, except the data in Ref. 73, the cross-section maxima are higher than in the present data. The displacement of the energy positions of the maxima is less pronounced in the experimental datasets than in the theoretical predictions. Earlier experimental works were further revised or revisited as discussed extensively in Refs. 4–6. The corrections applied to those experimental works due to undetected energetic fragments that are lost in the collection and

FIG. 11. Absolute single ionization cross-section of CF_4 σ_{TOTAL} of the present work in black solid squares compared to previous experimental data available in the literature as a function of the electron energy. The error bar is indicated on the 100 eV electron energy data.

detection steps and due to the inclusion of false events in the single ionization spectrum when for ion pair production one of the ions is not detected might have steadily overestimated the total and partial single ionization cross-sections.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, this work reports a new experimental methodology to extract absolute *PICS* and *TICS* using a recoil ion imaging technique (*RIMS*) and the relative flow technique (*RFT*). The method was validated through several test procedures and data comparisons with theoretical and experimental results available in the literature. Revisiting the theoretical results, these indicated that the cross-sections based on *BEB* and *DM* models are closely dependent on the electron-collision description and that the electron correlation always increases the *BEB* cross-sections.

The present experimental data are obtained with 4π solid angle acceptance for all ions, even with significant kinetic energies. Therefore, no corrections due to reduced transmission of the spectrometer are required, which is essential for the determination of precise absolute cross sections. The loss of energetic ions implies the requirement of ion trajectory simulations as a resource to correct the experimental deficiencies. For this purpose, previous knowledge of the kinetic energy distribution of the ions is needed, and this information is not always available. In the literature, cases are found where corrections of previous total and partial cross-section values were reported after the review of the signal processing and the addition of ion trajectory simulations and efficiency factors. These corrections have substantially affected the published experimental data. Therefore, the methodology presented here ensures the precise determination of absolute cross sections and minimizes the inclusion of correction factors, which would enhance inaccuracies.

Finally, the single ionization cross-sections provided in the present work are corrected for false events coming from ion-ion pair channels, that is, from dissociative double ionization. Therefore, the methodology presented here ensures the precise determination of

absolute cross sections and minimizes the inclusion of correction factors, which enhances inaccuracies.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

W. Wolff: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **M. Dogan:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **H. Luna:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **L. H. Coutinho:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **D. Mootheril:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Woonyong Baek:** Project administration (supporting); Resources (supporting); Writing – review & editing (equal). **T. Pfeifer:** Funding acquisition (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **A. Dorn:** Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data supporting this study are openly available. The research is declared as open access under license CCBY4.0.

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